

New coumarin from *Skimmia anquetelia*

Rajni Kant Sharma^a, Poonam Negi^a, Nisha Negi^a, Devendra S. Negi^{a*} and Hideaki Otsuka^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar (Garhwal)-246 174, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : devendra_negi@yahoo.com Fax : 91-1346-252174

^bDepartment of Pharmacognosy, Graduate School of Biomedical Sciences, Hiroshima University, 1-2-3 Kasumi, Minami-ku, Hiroshima 734-8553, Japan

Manuscript received 20 September 2007, revised 10 June 2008, accepted 8 July 2008

Abstract : A new coumarin isolated from leaves of *Skimmia anquetelia* has been identified as 6-methoxy-7-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methyl-butyl) coumarin.

Keywords : *Skimmia anquetelia*, coumarin.

Introduction

Skimmia (Rutaceae) species are rich in coumarins, coumarin glycosides, alkaloids, lupene derivative, and chromones¹⁻⁵. *Skimmia anquetelia* is an evergreen shrub generally distributed in Himalaya, East Asia and Philippines. Its leaves are traditionally chewed for cooling effect and mixed with other ingredients to manufacture incense 'dhup'⁶. We report isolation and structure determination of a new coumarin from *S. anquetelia*.

Results and discussion

The [M]⁺ of compound 1, *m/z* 264, corresponding to C₁₅H₁₈O₄ was determined by FAB mass spectrometry. The UV spectrum showed absorbance maxima at 240, 260 and 318 nm suggestive of hexaoxygenated coumarin. The IR spectrum indicated the presence of lactonyl functional group (1735 cm⁻¹) and aromatic nucleus (1596 cm⁻¹). A negative color reaction with alcoholic ferric chloride indicated absence of phenolic hydroxyl group.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of compound 1 displayed signals typical for 6-methoxy coumarin skeleton. Presence of two doublets at δ 6.23 (*J* 9.2 Hz) and 7.61 (*J* 9.2 Hz) and two aromatic singlets at δ 7.31 and 6.78 corresponded to 3, 4, 5, 8 unsubstituted coumarin along with one side chain and methoxy attached to it. The ¹H and ¹³C spectra indicated the presence of methyl substituted side chain by two upfield singlets at δ 1.10 and 1.27 and a doublet at 2.54 (*J* 10 Hz) assigned to benzyl methylene protons. ¹³C NMR spectrum along with DEPT experiment identified 15 carbon signals as five methine, two methyl, one

methoxy, one methylene, one carbonyl and five quaternary carbons. The molecular ion peak at 262 *m/z* corresponded to C₁₅H₁₈O₄ and other fragment ion peak at *m/z* 247 was due to loss of methyl group. The structure of 1 was thus elucidated as 6-methoxy-7-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methyl-butyl) coumarin.

Experimental

The leaves of *S. anquetelia* were collected from Tunghnath Chopta, Chamoli (Garhwal), Uttarakhand, India at 3200 meter height during flowering season and identified by Prof. R. D. Gaur, Taxonomist, Botany Department, HNB Garhwal University. A herbarium specimen has been in Botany Department, HNB Garhwal University, Srinagar, Uttarakhand. M.p. was measured in open capillary tube and is uncorrected. UV (MeOH) and IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer-Lambda 15 UV/VIS and Perkin-Elmer infrared 15 spectrophotometers, respectively. ¹H (400 MHz) and ¹³C (100 MHz) spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a JEOL α-400 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference. Mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX-102 mass spectrometer.

The shed dried and well ground leaves (3.4 kg) were refluxed with 90% ethanol and the extract was concentrated under reduced pressure. It was partitioned between n-hexane and methanol. The methanol-soluble fraction (76.4 g) was chromatographed over a column of silica gel and eluted with binary solution of CHCl_3 : MeOH in the sequence of increasing polarity. The compound was isolated from (hexane : ethyl acetate) CHCl_3 : MeOH (85 : 15, v/v) fraction as pale yellow solid (20 mg).

6-Methoxy-7-(2'-hydroxy-3'-methyl-butyl) coumarin (1) :

Pale yellow solid, m.p. 160–162 °C, UV (λ_{max}) (MeOH) : 240, 260, 318 nm^{-1} ; IR (ν_{max}) (KBr) : 3470, 1735, 1596, 910, 834 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz; CDCl_3) : δ 6.23 (1H, d, J 9.2 Hz, H-3), 7.61 (1H, d, J 9.2 Hz, H-4), 6.78 (1H, s, H-5), 7.31 (1H, s, H-8), 2.54 (2H, d, J 10.4 Hz, H-1'), 3.64 (1H, q, J 8.14 Hz, H-2'), 1.31 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.27 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.00 (3H, s, CH_3), in text 3.89 (3H, s, OCH_3); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz; CDCl_3) : δ 161.3 (C-2), 113.2 (C-3), 143.4 (C-4), 129.6 (C-5), 160.8 (C-6), 125.0 (C-7), 98.9 (C-8), 112.2 (C-4a), 154.9 (C-8a), 32.6 (C-1'), 73.0 (C-2'), 32.5 (C-3'), 26.4 (C-4'), 23.6 (C-1''), 56.0 (OCH_3); FAB-MS (m/z) 262

$[\text{M}]^+$, 285 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$, 263 $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, 247 $[\text{M}-\text{CH}_3]^+$, 204, 179, 167, 154, 136, 107, 95.

^{13}C DEPT : five methine, two methyl, one methoxy, one methylene, one carbonyl and five quaternary carbons.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to DST, Government of India for financial support. One of the authors would like to thank DST for scholarship.

References

1. J. Reisch and S. H. Achenbach, *Pharmazie*, 1992, **47**, 933.
2. A. U. Rahman, N. Sultana, M. I. Choudhary, P. M. Shah and M. R. Khan, *Journal of Natural Products*, 1998, **61**, 713.
3. T. K. Razdan, B. Qadri, S. Harkar and E. S. Waight, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 2063.
4. T. K. Razdan, S. Harkar, B. Qadri, M. A. Qurishi and M. A. Khuroo, *Phytochemistry*, 1988, **27**, 1890.
5. A. U. Rahman, N. Sultana, M. R. Khan and M. I. Choudhary, *Natural Product Letters*, 2002, **16**, 305.
6. R. D. Gaur, "Flora of District Garhwal of North West Himalaya", Transmedia Publication, Srinagar, 1999, p. 377.